

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

MODERN REQUIREMENTS IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

Like many countries, the share of agricultural products in the GDP of Azerbaijan is low. Despite this, this non-oil sector should be constantly focused on to ensure food security and meet the growing demand in the country. Regarding the growing demand of the population, it is not easy and impossible to meet the consumption of the population with completely natural products in recent times. The fact that the republic has nine of the existing climate types indicates the existence of the necessary conditions for agriculture. In the plain areas of the country, irrigation prevails, and in the mountainous and relatively foothills, the cultivation of wheat is predominant. The fact that animal husbandry requires more resources pushes us to tend towards agriculture like many developing countries. Each economic region in the country has its own specialized agricultural area. Like most developing countries, Azerbaijan's population growth rate is positive. This means that the mentioned issue will become more difficult in the coming years. At present, it is undeniable that the population of Azerbaijan is involved in the supply of food products at the expense of imports of some necessary goods. The development of today's technologies will forever change our understanding of the agricultural sector. The most important technological phenomenon of our time has been the droneization of agriculture. All possible measures should be taken for the development of the agrarian sector, considering the damage caused to people's health by genetically modified products imported into the country.

Keywords: agriculture, crop production, agricultural productivity, geographic information system, environment, unmanned aerial vehicles, technology development.

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The purpose of the study.

In modern times, the role of science in all fields is undeniable, and agriculture should also be added here. Thus, it is important to record or conduct statistics that reflect the entire development and process, including achievements such as the discovery of new methods, the discovery of new and more productive plant and animal species in the agricultural field. Because it is convenient to determine the efficiency of any work and to make predictions for the future with these indicators, which consider the past and past activities.

The role of agriculture in the country's economy

The special importance of the agricultural sector for the country's economy is determined by its direct impact on all types of economic activity. Thus, the need for various types of agricultural machinery stimulates the development of machine-building, the need to use mineral fertilizers activates the chemical industry. In addition, the agricultural sector plays an exceptional role in ensuring the country's food security and food independence.

In addition, there are a number of factors that hinder the innovative development of the agricultural sector of the economy:

As a result, many agricultural enterprises (especially in tea cultivation) cannot use traditional sources of financing (bank loans, borrowing on capital markets, etc.). In addition, in the conditions of limited budget funding, it is appropriate to implement financing schemes that ensure the distribution of risks among the participants of the innovation process of agricultural producers, as well as the use of protection mechanisms against these risks;

- structural disorganization of the innovation process. Currently, there is no effective system for the transfer of innovations to production, because the interaction of innovators, public authorities and investors is very difficult;

- innovation is limited and usually only a small part of large and economically strong farms exist. In the current conditions, it is necessary to increase innovation and investments in agriculture, which will be further facilitated by the implementation of measures of the state's innovative policy in agriculture[2]. The most important goal of the state innovation policy in the agro-industrial complex is to create conditions for effective innovation at all levels.

The set of measures for the implementation of the state innovation policy in the agro-industrial complex is determined by the transformations that ensure the development of new progressive forms of innovative activity, taking into account the characteristics of agricultural production.

First of all, special attention should be paid to the formation of legislative and regulatory mechanisms that will facilitate the flow of innovations in the agricultural sector. It is necessary to prepare laws and other regulatory documents defining the attitude of the state to the development of innovative processes in the agricultural sector, directions and measures of state support, as well as to create favorable conditions for investing in innovative activities.

In agriculture, it plays an extremely important role in the socio-economic and political tasks of the state, especially in the field of employment of people living in the regions. As a result of the negative impact of the processes in the large energy market on the economy of Azerbaijan, examples of layoffs in other sectors of the economy are considered to be the agricultural sector. The formation of the agricultural department in our country in real time provides opportunities for as many people as possible in this field. Taking into account the development of agriculture in the private sector, in the period 1992-1995, advanced agricultural production in the agrarian sector decreased by 12 percent, and since 1996 (excluding 1997 and 2014), the increase was 6.6 percent. In 2015, the growth of animal production was 2.5%, and crop production was 11.3%. At present, one of the main problems in the development of livestock stock in our republic is poor food supply. An internal account to improve the sale of animals from the sale of an animal, to significantly affect the generation of income. For example, chicken problems in chicken are only described. It should be noted that in recent years animal feed has become one of the fastest growing international developments[3]. The increase in global

food demand has necessitated the implementation of a development policy in this field in Azerbaijan.

In general, the development of agriculture in Azerbaijan is possible. The figures of the first 6 months of 2018 show that agriculture increased by 3.1 percent against the backdrop of a decrease in GDP in the country. During this period, the actual value of agricultural goods was 2,500.9 million manats, 57.4 percent of the agricultural sector was produced by the livestock sector, and 42.6 percent by plant production. According to the events of the World Bank, the country is poorer in oil development in 2019 and 4% by 2017, and legal records by 2020-2022. The World Bank and other international organizations, of course, emphasize in the section on the increasing non-oil oil competition in the agricultural sector, which is important for the dynamic development of the country. Legal notice and sale of value demonstrate agricultural production in terms of added production value. This type of fuel. The 30 largest farms in the country are 19 places in the Hecht area. Farmers created one hectare per hectare and increased up to 60% of the liter of Legal Presentation in the warnings and wheat Entente-120. Therefore, estimates of fuel cell phones look at wheat income in next year's production. By 2023, wheat imports were predicted to decrease by 31.15% in the first six months.

Innovative measures in agriculture

Ensuring the economic security of the state is a response to calls to prevent it from becoming a threat. Currently, humanity is facing problems such as climate change, population aging, global food security, which dictate the need for rapid development of certain areas of research and technological development ("clean" energy, genomic medicine, new technologies in agriculture, etc.). In order to respond to these challenges, it is necessary to integrate Azerbaijan deeper into the global innovation system.

Two development options of the agro-industrial complex can be presented - inertial and innovative [4]. Inertial selection ensures the preservation of existing economic mechanisms, the extent of state support, as well as investment opportunities and, accordingly, the growth rate of the total agricultural output.

With an innovative choice, accelerated socio-economic development will be realized to a large extent by using modernization opportunities for existing production, and the transition to the implementation of innovative developments will be accelerated. The differences between the two scenarios are:

- volume and direction of investments at the level of state support to agriculture;
- in the share of products using resource-saving technologies or innovative technologies;
- in terms of economy and competitiveness of products in the domestic market;
- in the share of exported agricultural products and food;
- in terms of the social situation of the rural population and the development of agriculture.

The main reason for the change in the structure of agricultural financing sources is a sharp change in the state financing policy in all areas predetermined by radical changes in the economy.

Among the producers of agricultural products, a small part is occupied by farms whose production is based on innovation and belongs to the latest technological structure. These are mainly tea cultivation, cultivation of citrus fruits, and indoor plant growing enterprises. At the other end, there are private subsistence farms and small farms that use mainly manual labor, primitive backward technologies and are not secondary[5]. Among them there are various agricultural organizations and large peasant (farm) holdings that require modernization, mainly related to the third and fourth structures.

Currently, about 1.5% of large agricultural organizations that use modern agricultural machinery and technologies, including seeds, have advanced techniques and technologies in less than 0.5% of their (peasant) holdings. Moreover, they efficiently produce more than 10% of all agricultural products in the country[6].

The statistics shows the change of the total amount of investments directed to the fixed capital in the sectors of the economy in the Republic of Azerbaijan during the years 2010-2023 and the share falling on the rural economy. Taking into account that the volume of these investments was formed mainly due to the income from oil, accordingly, the growth of investments started from 2013 and continued growth is observed until 2019, which is considered one of the most successful periods in terms of oil. If there are some decreases after 2019, by 2023, the highest indicator of total investment has been reached again. Looking at the recent periods, a very large increase is observed compared to the first periods of independence.

It should be noted that the modernization of agricultural production and the transition to innovative development, energy and resource saving technologies can be accompanied by mass job liberalization. In this regard, much attention should be paid to diversification, opening of new jobs, retraining of personnel and organization of alternative activities in rural areas.

In order to restore production and social infrastructure, it is necessary to attract both Azerbaijani and foreign investment along with budget funds. It is necessary to attract investment by creating a favorable investment environment in the country, direct budget support for agriculture, favorable credit and tax conditions for companies investing in rural economy, and temporary exemption from income tax on the condition that large investments are made in rural development.

Until recently, agriculture was the most traditional sector of the economy. Any innovations took root here slowly; technological cycles were too long. The development of today's technologies will forever change our understanding of the agricultural sector. The most important technological phenomenon of our time has been the droneization of agriculture [7].

Drones increase the efficiency of monitoring the condition of fields and crops. Today it is carried out using manned aircraft, satellites and even simply walking around fields with measuring instruments.

This takes a lot of time and resources. The main problem with this approach is data systematization: a very labor-intensive and long-term process. Thanks to drones, more information can be collected and processed much faster, which leads to increased profitability and improved yields[8]. The transition to the use of drones will save farmers from exhausting walks across the field with special measuring instruments, and will also help with collecting data on the condition of crops at any time.

Currently, a state program for the development of agriculture and the regulation of agricultural products, raw materials and food markets should be prepared, which should include the following measures:

- renewal of the park of agricultural machinery;
- energy saving and energy efficiency improvement in agriculture;
- modernization of machine testing stations;
- development of agricultural consulting system in municipalities;
- creation and development of innovation centers.

The main indicators of the implementation of this program should be the following:

- volume of purchase of basic types of equipment by agricultural organizations;
- testing volume of agricultural machinery and equipment by machine testing stations;
- the share of energy resources produced by agricultural organizations using renewable energy sources;
- the number of regional agricultural consulting organizations and innovation centers;
- the proportion of organizations implementing technological innovations in agriculture and food production.

In my opinion, innovation policy in the agro-industrial complex should be aimed at solving the following problems.

1. Creating an attractive financial and investment environment for foreign direct investment in agriculture. This can be helped by state financing of concessions as a national priority in agriculture, lending to science, and the main directions of scientific and technological progress. In addition, the law on the protection of intellectual property needs to be implemented. Reforming patent laws would make the mechanism for transferring intellectual property from public to private entities more transparent. Improvement of technical regulations, tax regime, simplified licensing procedure, certification and liberalization of labor legislation will create more attractive conditions for innovation.

2. Use of innovative potential. In order to solve this problem, it is necessary to create an optimal combination of public and private sectors in science, high-tech fields, market-based innovative mechanisms that create and spread competitiveness.

3. Creating conditions for the priority development of the agro-industrial complex. It is necessary to implement state protectionism in relation to innovative infrastructure enterprises, ensure legal regulation and stimulation of agriculture, and increase the

role and responsibility of all levels of the government in the implementation of the state's innovative policy.

4. Development of personnel potential of the agro-industrial complex. It is necessary to solve the problems of improving the conditions and processes for receiving vocational education, adapting the established professional abilities of graduates of educational institutions to the professional requirements of innovative production, achieving a balanced demand in the labor market, and improving the supply of young specialists to agricultural enterprises. The specificity of the agricultural sector is conditioned by the fact that sometimes there is a need to finance experimental research, the results of which show themselves for many years. In other words, funds allocated for scientific research sometimes stimulate scientific and innovative innovations, which are necessary for further economic development for a long time.

As for Azerbaijan, it is currently recognized at the government level that the mechanisms of financing scientific and research works in the agricultural field do not meet the requirements of the time[9]. However, it is not the right approach to mask the current problems in this field with general words such as "lack of funds". In fact, a lot of work can be done within the existing possibilities, it is possible to get out of the inertia and provincial atmosphere and develop new research methods.

Experience shows that it is crucial to have the personnel potential that meets modern requirements in the field of reliable supply of food products to the population. The level of professional training of highly and medium-skilled agricultural specialists in terms of modern requirements is still low. In order for these specialties to be attractive in rural areas, it is necessary to implement appropriate measures and solve the socio-economic problems of specialists.

Conclusion

Today, the modernization measures implemented in the agrarian field are considered an important factor in ensuring the irreversibility of the quality-oriented reforms implemented in agriculture, which is one of the priority areas of the national economy in Azerbaijan, in improving the socio-economic development of the modern village, and at the same time in adapting the production and social infrastructure to modern requirements. Such development includes a set of measures aimed at ensuring uninterrupted economic growth in agriculture and its inter-related areas.

Thus, it is possible to increase the efficiency of agricultural production and ensure food security only on the basis of the operation of a highly developed material and technical base and its renewal, that is, modernization of farms with new engineering products and re-equipment of equipment, creation of a complex of mechanization and automation machines.

Modernization enables the transition to an innovative development model, compensates for the negative consequences of the global economic crisis, and increases the competitiveness of local agriculture through the wide application of advanced technologies in agricultural engineering, crop and livestock production and processing industry.

Drones have great potential in terms of optimizing agricultural production. Their main advantage is simplified access to other technologies that will allow them to grow more and spend less not only for large agricultural holdings, but also for farmers. In many countries around the world, drones are already being used to monitor plant quality. This is still a new product in Azerbaijan, but the first companies have already appeared that offer services such as flying over cultivated areas, analyzing and drawing up specific recommendations for plant care, as well as biological plant protection.

Special attention should be paid to the issues of state support for innovation, organization of an effective mechanism that can concentrate investment resources on priority areas of agriculture, creation of conditions for the introduction of innovations in the agricultural sector, and personnel training for innovation.

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